

St. Dominic College of Asia's Bachelor of Science in Accountancy and Bachelor of Science in Accounting Technology employment tracer study

Selica Misty N. Navarrete*

Admissions Office, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: mnavarrete@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

This study discusses the results of the employment tracer study of the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) and Bachelor of Science in Accounting Technology (BSAT) graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia who graduated between 2016 and 2021. The objectives of this tracer study are to determine the following: the demographic profile of the respondents, the length of their job search, and their current employment status. A quantitative approach was used in this study, wherein 27 out of 122 graduates from 2016 to 2021 provided their responses on the survey questionnaire given to them. Results show that the majority of the graduates were hired less than a month after their graduation. In addition, most of them were employed at their jobs through a recommendation from someone. Most of the respondents are currently employed and are working in the private sector.

Keywords: Bachelor of Science in Accountancy; Bachelor of Science in Accounting Technology; employment; tracer study.

To cite this article:

Navarrete, S. M. N. (2021). St. Dominic College of Asia's Bachelor of Science in Accountancy and Bachelor of Science in Accounting Technology employment tracer study. *SDCA Journal of Accountancy*, 2, 9-15.

Introduction

A graduate tracer study is a highly efficient instrument that can yield important data, which helps keep track, allowing the institution to observe if the right skills and knowledge are provided to their graduates (Cuadra et al., 2019). To enhance their curricula and demonstrate to prospective students how their graduates successfully made the shift to the workforce, educational institutions are also becoming increasingly interested in getting input from their former students. One or two years following graduation, graduates are typically asked for feedback on their experiences in the job market. In terms of quality assurance, the data from this tracer research may be utilized for the institution's further development (Schomburg, 2016).

Parents and prospective students can be educated by a tracer study, which also makes information helpful for career counseling. It can help the institution find a way to collect information, which can further improve the curriculum, output, activities, and programs for current and potential graduate students. Bueno (2017) said that using tracer studies is essential in order to revisit the curriculum of the program, which could enhance the alignment between higher education and the job market. According to Sanders (2018), it is best to classify the group status of graduate students by updating the data to ensure their performance and growth in their respective careers.

Several tracer studies were conducted to determine the current status of graduates from different schools and universities across the world. Siraye et al. (2018) evaluated a tracer study on the employment status of business and economics graduates from a private university in Ethiopia and found that identifying problems and making decisions in a short time period were skills with the highest mean weighted discrepancy score and a high need for curriculum enhancement. Munro and Senekal (2019) conducted a

literature review of 23 graduate tracer studies from 13 countries from 1995 to 2016 and suggested three models to create a graduate tracer research study in a South African context. Another study in Ghana by Nudzor and Ansah (2020) was made in which the researchers discovered challenges in conducting graduate tracer studies, such as the difficulty in accessing alumni records, obsession with publications, absence of a reliable database on graduates, wide physical geographic coverage, lengthy survey questionnaires, and difficulty in associating graduate employment success with study courses.

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, Alfonso et al. (2020) conducted a tracer study on the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Accounting Technology program at City College of Angeles, wherein most of the graduates from this school were able to land their jobs according to their course, which resulted in their contentment in their respective careers. On the other hand, Catacutan et al. (2020) showed a tracer study of the Business Administration graduates from a private higher education institution in Tuguegarao and found that the university was able to produce highly competent graduates who are professionally ready to work, as they were holistically developed when they were studying at that university.

The requirement that education and training be adapted to the present and future requirements of countries going through social and economic transformation is a basic issue with these programs. Education and training must be flexibly arranged within the constantly changing framework rather than according to rigid requirements. It is flexible and needs to be so at all times. To be able to make the best use of limited resources, it must also be made sure that the unique circumstances of the nation are taken into consideration, ensuring that training and education are made effective (Hazaymeh & Dela Peña, 2015; Schomburg, 2016).

Methodology

A quantitative method was used in this study. From 2016 to 2021, graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) and Bachelor of Science in Accounting Technology (BSAT) programs at St. Dominic College of Asia produced 122 alumni members, but only 27 were able to answer the researcher-made survey questionnaire, which was the main instrument in the study. The study was conducted at the end of the second semester of the academic year 2020–2021.

Table 1. Respondents of the study according to year graduated

Year Graduated	Total No. of Graduates	Total No. of Respondents
2016	15	3
2017	18	1
2018	32	7
2019	21	3
2020	22	4
2021	14	9
Total	122	27

The tracer study questionnaire was distributed to the respondents online via a Google Form. The researcher communicated with them through email, text message, and social media. The questionnaire is composed of three (3) parts: a demographic profile, an employment history, and the current employment status. The results were then analyzed using frequency distribution and percentage to determine the demographic profile and the length of the job search, including how the graduates found their first job.

Results and Discussion

The tables below discuss the results of the study based on the data gathered and collected.

*A. Demographic Profile***Table 2.** Age (n=27)

Age (years old)	f	%
23	2	7.41%
24	4	14.81%
25	10	37.04%
26	5	18.52%
29	1	3.70%
30 and above	5	18.52%

Table 2 shows that in terms of age, most of the respondents (10 or 37.04%) are 25 years old while five (5) respondents each for 26 years old and 30 and above. This is followed by 24 years old with four (4) respondents (14.81%). Two (2) respondents (7.41%) answered 23 years old and only one (1) or 3.70% is a 29 year old respondent.

Table 3. Gender (n=27)

Gender	f	%
Male	5	18.52%
Female	22	81.48%

Table 3 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the gender of the respondents. Majority (81.48%) of the respondents are females while the remaining participants (18.52%) are males.

Table 4. Civil status (n=27)

Civil Status	f	%
Single	26	96.30%
Married	1	3.70%

This table above shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the civil status of the respondents. Majority (26 or 96.30%) of the respondents are single while only one (1) or 3.70% is married.

Table 5. Year graduated (n=27)

Year Graduated	f	%
2016	3	11.11%
2017	1	3.70%
2018	7	25.93%
2019	3	11.11%
2020	4	14.81%
2021	9	33.33%

Table 5 shows that most of the respondents of the study graduated between the years of 2016 and 2021. There are nine (9) respondents (33.33%) who graduated in 2021. This is followed by seven (7) respondents (25.93%) who graduated in 2018. Four (4) respondents (14.81%) graduated in 2020 while three (3) respondents (11.11%) in 2016 and 2019, respectively. Only one (1) respondent graduated in 2017.

B. Employment History**Table 6.** Length of job search (n=27)

Length of Job Search	f	%
Less than a month	12	44.44%
1 month-6 months	11	40.74%
7 months-11 months	2	7.41%
1 year to less than 2 years	1	3.70%
3 years to less than 4 years	1	3.70%

Table 6 shows that the majority of the graduates or 12 respondents (44.44%) were hired in just less than a month after graduation, while 40.74% (11 respondents) were hired within one (1) month to six (6) months. Two (2) respondents (7.41%) hired in seven (7) to 11 months and 3.70% (1 respondent) for both hired in one (1) to less than two (2) years and three (3) years to less than four (4) years.

Table 7. Means of finding the first job (n=27)

Means	f	%
Walk-in application	3	11.11%
Job fair	2	7.41%
Information from friends / relatives	8	29.63%
Recommended by someone	10	37.04%
Advertisement	4	14.81%

Results in Table 7 answers the question “*How did you find your first job?*” It shows that 10 respondents (37.04%) found their respective jobs through recommendation from someone. There are 8 respondents (29.63%) who found their jobs through information from friends or relatives. Four (4) respondents (14.81%) were hired through advertisements while three (3) respondents (11.11%) hired through walk-in applications. While the remaining two (2) respondents (7.41%) found their job through job fairs.

C. Current Employment Status**Table 8.** Current employment status (n=27)

Employment Status	f	%
Employed	24	88.89%
Not Employed	3	11.11%

According to the table above, 88.89% (24) of the respondents are currently employed as shown in Table 6. 11.11% (3 respondents) are not employed.

Table 9. Type of sector of the current company (n=27)

Sector	f	%
Government	1	3.70%
Private	20	74.07%
Non-government organization	2	7.41%
Not applicable	2	7.41%
Others	2	7.41%

Table 9 shows that 20 respondents (74.07%) are hired in a private sector while two (2) respondents (7.41%) hired under non-government organizations and others. Only one (1) respondent is hired in a government organization, while two (2) of them did not specify their sector.

Table 10. Nature of business of the current employment (n=27)

Sector	f	%
Accounting Services	5	18.52%
Banking and Finance	1	3.70%
Customer Service	1	3.70%
Development Communication	1	3.70%
Education / Training	1	3.70%
Food and Beverage	2	7.41%
Outsourcing	3	11.11%
Public Relations / Public Information	2	7.41%
Sales / Marketing	3	11.11%
Tourism and Hospitality Industry	1	3.70%
Not Applicable	2	7.41%
Others	5	18.52%

Results in Table 10 that respondents working in the accounting services industry with five (5) respondents (18.52%), while also five (5) respondents (18.52%) answered others. There are three (3) respondents (11.11%) who work in the field of outsourcing. There are two (2) respondents (7.41%) who answered public relations and those with 'not applicable.' Lastly each of the respondent (3.70%) also works for the following industries: banking and finance, customer service, development communication, education and training, and the tourism and hospitality industry.

Table 11. Relatedness of the current roles to the field of training in college (n=27)

Relatedness	f	%
Related	23	85.19%
Not Related	4	14.81%

In Table 11, results show that most of the graduates perceived that their current roles in their respective jobs match their field of training in SDCA. 85.19% (23 respondents) of them agree that their current roles are related to their field of training in college while 14.81% (4 respondents) said that their field of training is not related at all.

Table 12. Current job position (n=27)

Job Position	f	%
Rank-and-File	24	88.89%
Supervisory Level	2	7.41%
Managerial Level	1	3.70%

Results show in Table 12 that most of the graduates are working at a rank-and-file level with 24 respondents (88.89%). There are two (2) respondents (7.41%) in the supervisory positions while there are also one (1) respondent (3.70%) who are working at the managerial level.

Table 13. Current tenure of employment (n=27)

Tenure	f	%
Contractual	4	14.81%
Regular / Permanent	16	59.26%
Temporary / Probationary	5	18.52%
N/A	2	7.41%

Table 13 discusses the current tenure of employment of the graduates of SDCA. Results show that 16 respondents (59.26%) are regular and permanent employees while there are four (4) respondents (14.81%) working as contractual employees. There are five (5) respondents (18.52%) working as temporary and probationary status while two respondents answered, ‘not applicable.’

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the BSA and BSAT alumni of St. Dominic College of Asia from 2016 to 2021 are mostly 25 years old, female, and single. Alumni members are highly employable; therefore, they were able to find jobs in less than a month and found their jobs through a recommendation from someone. The graduates of SDCA under the BSA and BSAT programs are mostly employed in the private sector as rank-and-file and regular employees. This study recommends that there should be another, more extensive tracer study conducted, which must cover more respondents and use a comprehensive data-gathering approach. Moreover, the result of this study allows the BSA and BSAT programs to consider further improving the curriculum and instruction.

References

- Alfonso, R. O., Bautista, K. N., Berdos, M. P., Bustamante, P. M. F., Nuqui, A. J. S., Papio, J. C., & Abello, L. M. (2020). Tracer study: BS in accounting technology graduates of City College of Angeles. *Punla*, 3, 197-208.
<https://cca.edu.ph/assets/images/Tracer%20Study%20BS%20in%20Accounting%20Technology%20Graduates%20of%20City%20College%20of%20Angeles.pdf>
- Bueno, D. C. (2017). Ascertaining the curriculum relevance of the graduate school through tracer study in a Philippine private higher education institution. *JPAIR Multidisciplinary Research*, 28(1), 72-88.
<https://doi.org/10.7719/jpair.v28i1.502>
- Catacutan, K. J. A., Maramag, F. R. A., Bartolome, M. A., Hiquiana, R. M., & Mendezabal, M. J. (2020). Employability study of the business administration graduates of Catholic educational institution. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(1), 156-161.
<https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080119>
- Cuadra, L. J., Aure, M. R. K. L., & Gonzaga, G. L. (2019). The use of tracer study in improving undergraduate programs in the university. *Asia Pacific Higher Education Research Journal (APHERJ)*, 6(1), 13-25.
<https://po.pnuresearchportal.org/ejournal/index.php/apherj/article/view/1315/409>
- Hazaymeh, E. N. M., & Dela Peña, M. K. (2015). A tracer study of La Salle University College of Engineering graduates. *Lasallian Research Forum*, 18(1), 52-68.
https://www.academia.edu/34769329/Vol_18_No_1_A_Tracer_Study_of_La_Salle_University_College_of_Engineering_Graduates
- Munro, N., & Senekal, J. (2019). Lessons learnt from two decades of graduate tracer research: Recommendations for the South African context. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 33(2), 230-248. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC-16ae7a2a32>

- Nudzor, H. P., & Ansah, F. (2020). Enhancing post-graduate programme effectiveness through tracer studies: The reflective accounts of a Ghanaian nation-wide graduate tracer study research team. *Quality in Higher Education*, 26(2), 192-208. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2020.1763034>
- Sanders, B. (2018). *Student outcomes survey: Self-reported graduate model review*. National Centre for Vocational Education Research. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED581488.pdf>
- Schomburg, H. (2016). *Carrying out tracer studies – Guide to anticipating and matching skills and jobs (Vol. 6)*. Publications Office of the European Union. https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/m/45A4CE81F3398029C1258048005BEFB8_Vol.%206%20Carrying%20out%20tracer%20studies.pdf
- Siraye, Z., Abebe, T., Melese, M., & Wale, T. (2018). A tracer study on employability of business and economics graduates at Bahir Dar University. *International Journal of Higher Education and Sustainability*, 2(1), 45-63. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJHES.2018.092406>